

THE APPLICATION OF ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES TO IMPROVE MINING AND TUNNELING PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays digital technology plays a very important role in Mining/ Tunneling technology. There are various methods to improve the productivity of mining/ tunneling and complete the successive activities in time and budget. This article is based to find out how various analytical methods are used to improve mining/ tunneling productivity.

Key words: Mining Technology, Tunneling, data analyses, analytical methods

1. INTRODUCTION

Tunnel boring is one of the critical activities in most of the Mining Construction Projects & Underground Metro Project. Hence, tunneling/ mining works are given high priority in the Underground Metro Project as well as in other projects such as mining and other underground construction projects. To complete the project as per agreed baseline schedule tunneling/ mining works must be completed as per the plan so that successive activities such as Track Laying, Cable Trays, Electrical works, mechanical works, systems installation works can be completed as per schedule. There is various mining technology to improve tunneling/ mining/ boring. However, there are some simple data analyses methods through which the real issues can be identified and can be resolved in time to increase the boring rate.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW:

In the book Underground Infrastructure for Sustainable Urban Growth (2013), Chapter: 6 Innovative Sustainable Underground Technology and Infrastructure. There are various factors for analytical computation methods are considered such as:

Analytical and Computational Methods:

Analytical methods — primarily confined-form mathematical approaches that really don't entail something like a computer — for measuring tensions, stretches, groundwater motions, surface runoff, and some other attributes are essential to enhancing understanding of the characteristics of underground structures in conjunction with groundwater. They include data on underground structures' responses to specific idealised boundary conditions and material behaviour. Analytical methods do seem to be crucial tools for developing knowledge and judgement on geotechnical

behaviour, conducting preliminary design studies (or complete design with appropriate configurations) and comparing complex computational model outputs to assess reliability. They can not however capture the complete sophistication of most shallow foundations and geological formations.

Computational methods like finite elements, finite differences, and discrete element methods are being used to guesstimate soil, groove, or architected structure behaviours when there is sufficient detailed information available — for example, to refine response-based design — but can be useful if there is limited background professional experience under particular circumstances. The use of computer software programmes will predict behaviours. Computational methods can now be used, for instance, to measure structure-ground encounters and abrasions, adjustments in the soil environment (e.g., thermal shifts and groundwater flow and leakage), and the spread of smoke and fire in occupied underwater welding. All computational methods, for certain if premised on discretion (e.g., imbalance versus important contributor) or stability presumptions (e.g., continuum, discrete rock blocks, or some hybrid), make sense in the context of geospatial data and metals properties (e.g. intact materials, deformations, and fluid properties). However, some easy analytical method can also be introduced to improve the mining productivity which are handy to use

III. OBJECTIVE

The objective of this study is to provide some innovative analytical data analyses techniques to improve mining / tunneling productivity.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Qualitative method is carried out by accessing some of the expert's opinion who were having experience in various mining / tunneling construction activities.

V. DATA ANALYSES

Qualitive data analyses has been done and the expert opinion has been considered to come to a logical conclusion. Following are the various techniques that has been considered after discussion with the expert focus groups. Various data analyses techniques are illustrated below

Round Time Analyses:

One of such data analyses tools is Round Time Analyses which is used to analyses the progress and improve the drilling performance for Mining/ Tunnel project. Most drill and blast tunnels / mines have almost the same pattern of repetitive movements such as drilling blast holes, detonating the blast followed by ventilation to eliminate gases, removing blast rocks (mucking), scaling the crown and walls to eliminate loosened rock pieces, installing initial ground support, etc as shown in the figure.

As the process is cyclic, all the intermediate phases need to be completed at an appropriate duration which is analyzed before while preparing the baseline schedule for tunneling works. In this figure, one cycle is taking approximately 8 hrs. So, 3 cycles should be completed in a day (24hrs.).

As per this figure, the cycle time which took more than 8 hrs. need to be analyzed to identify the reasons for delay and recommended mitigations to be applied for future mining/tunneling. Analyzing the complete cycle gives a broad picture so each phase can be analyzed separately so that the real deficiency can be identified and solved to improve mining/ tunneling progress.

Time Chainage Diagram:

Another data analyses method is Time chainage diagram which can demonstrate the overall plan in a page and is used to analyses the plan versus actual for overall mining/ tunneling packages and other linear construction projects. This type of analyses is also used for high rise building, depot construction, highway construction. The Diagram is used to optimize the resources in regard to the progress rates. This tool is also used to prepare as-built schedule and help to analyses the Time Impact Analyses of the project. A sample Time Chainage Diagram is shown in the figure.

Gap Analyses:

Gap analyses is also a data analyses tool that can be used to identify the problem for the activities that are behind the schedule, identify the issue to recommend a better mitigation plan for those problematic activities so that the mining/ tunneling work as per schedule. For example, the chart

shows there is a gap/ variance of 11% between plan and actual. The reason behind this variance can be analyzed by conducting a meeting or by interviewing the Mining Engineer/ Site Engineer and recommend the new asking rate with the solutions as required for that mine/ tunnel.

VI Results:

There are many simple data analyses techniques which can help to increase the productivity of mining/ tunneling work and are very user friendly and easily computable.

VII Conclusion:

In conclusion, there are various data analyses techniques which can be used to monitor progress, identify shortfalls, analyze variance, improve the interface between various contractors and stakeholders. Real and actual data input is the key for data analyses

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